

THE INFLUENCE OF TOBACCO SMOKING ON PSYCHOPHYSIOLOGICAL FUNCTIONS IN THE BODY OF YOUNG PEOPLE

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Annotation: Smoking tobacco products contributes to the development of diseases and premature death in representatives of the able-bodied population. Numerous studies indicate the adverse effects of smoking on young people, including students and students in all developed countries. Thus, according to research data, the risk factors for smoking among students include: low socio-economic status, smoking relatives, a positive opinion about smoking of friends and classmates, inability to continue education, high availability of tobacco products and aggressive behavior of the individual. In the USA, stress, the desire to lose weight, high anxiety, depressive states, and the influence of advertising are also considered significant factors of motivation to smoke. Alcohol is also a contributing factor to smoking.

Keywords: electroencephalogram, indicators lower, remaining segments

In the course of the first series of surveys, we identified a group of young men who smoke using the survey method. An electroencephalogram was recorded in this group after smoking a cigarette. Smoking one cigarette led to an increase in slow-wave activity on the delta- and theta-wave electroencephalogram in the frontal, occipital and temporal leads at the end of the five-minute period after smoking compared with the initial encephalogram. In the initial period, on the contrary, there was an increase in the power of the alpha wave spectrum in most leads and a decrease in the power of slow waves.

Thus, the results of the study indicate the undoubted influence of smoking on the psychophysiological functions of the body. Our data confirm the negative effect

of substances contained in tobacco smoke on the functions of the central nervous system. The facts of gender differences in this influence are of practical interest. Thus, in young men at this age stage, there is an unevenness of adaptive compensatory changes in the body, expressed in an increase in the speed of simple psychomotor reactions and a decrease in complex ones. The girls in the smoking group had all the indicators lower, both in comparison with the non-smoking group and with the boys in their group. The identified gender differences should be taken into account when developing programs to create motivation for a healthy lifestyle and smoking cessation in adolescent and youth population groups.

The components of motivation to quit smoking were also identified — negative physiological sensations, disappointment in certain benefits from smoking, awareness of the illogicality of smoking, serious diseases in the future. At the same time, for different groups of smokers, there is a different set of incentives to refuse, which determines a differentiated approach to the impact on smokers in the framework of anti-smoking measures.

The results of such a study may be the basis for the development of anti-smoking measures. An urgent and promising scientific problem is the study of the socio-psychological factors of the primary refusal of smoking and the psychological characteristics of non-smokers (potential smokers).

Part of the questionnaire was devoted to the motives of smoking, respondents assessed the impact of each factor on tobacco consumption on a 5-point scale. It turned out that the strongest motives for smoking on average in the sample are the ability to relieve stress and relax through smoking (3.55 points), as well as habit (3.45 points). The next most important motives for smoking are nicotine addiction (2.94 points) and smoking "for company" (2.81 points). Such a motive as the opportunity to feel grown-up and confident to enhance attractiveness in the eyes of the opposite sex is estimated at 1.50 points.

To determine the latent factors indirectly affecting tobacco smoking, a factor analysis based on smoking was performed. The first factor was called "Capitalization of the I-brand", because it added an image of "seriousness" and aggregated variables such as "a cigarette makes me more businesslike", "it looks sexy and young people like it", "smoking for me is a protest or a challenge to others", "a cigarette helps to feel the fullness of life", "a cigarette helps me to get acquainted, to start communicating with someone." The second factor was called "Habit" by us. It includes variables such as "I have developed an addiction to nicotine", "I already smoke automatically, out of habit", "a cigarette helps me take ("kill") time". Consumers are involved in smoking without having a pronounced incentive to smoke, to overcome the monotony of the time of forced waiting. The third factor is "Social". It includes variables of solidarity and conformity: "my whole environment smokes", "I often smoke for the company", "I don't want to fight off the collective". The fourth factor — the "Mental State Regulator"— combines variables such as "a cigarette helps me concentrate" and "a cigarette helps to relieve stress and relax." The respondents of the third group ("irrational smokers" — 33.7%) have no pronounced leading incentives to smoking (the average values of all factors are less than 0). They do not smoke out of habit, not automatically, but quite consciously. To the clarifying question: "Why do you smoke?" — they answer: "Just like that, but I can quit at any time."

Smokers of the fourth group ("smokers-image makers" — 12.1%) have the most pronounced motivation to build their own image with notes of demonstrativeness in behavior. It is noteworthy that it is the female image-makers who have a relatively low desire to quit smoking, which indicates that this motive is the strongest in tobacco consumption. In the remaining segments (groups identified as a result of segmentation), tobacco users have a strong desire to quit smoking. So, on average, 64.3% of respondents confirm their willingness to give up smoking in the sample.

The tobacco smoking experience is largely interrelated with the smoker's belonging to a particular group (this conclusion is based on the analysis of the conjugacy tables). In Table 1, it can be seen that with an increase in the duration of smoking, the proportion of social smokers and hedonistic smokers changes: from an insignificant level of manifestation (9% and 12%, respectively) to the predominant (30% and 60%, respectively). Thus, it is possible to draw a very important conclusion in understanding the motivation of tobacco smoking about the migration of segments (the change in the affiliation of smokers from one segment to another): as the smoking experience increases, such segments as "social smokers" and "hedonistic smokers" prevail. Since the consumers of these segments differ in the presence of a longer dependence on smoking, this confirms us in the need for preventive measures.

The study of the motives for quitting smoking contributes to understanding the levers of influence on the consumer behavior of smokers. In this regard, along with determining the most significant reasons for quitting smoking, as well as the most perceived disadvantages from tobacco use, the questionnaire used the question "What are the most significant reasons for your desire to quit smoking?", to which a number of answer options were offered. The most frequently mentioned reasons for possible smoking cessation in descending order are as follows: the desire to give birth to a healthy child (81%), unwillingness to face serious diseases of the cardiovascular system and lungs (80%), tangible costs for the purchase of cigarettes (56%), unpleasant ingrained tobacco smell from hair and clothes (53%), the desire to live longer (51%) and awareness of the fact of dependence on a bad habit — smoking cigarettes (50%). It should be noted that the first two reasons for refusal as the most possible were chosen mainly by consumers with a long smoking experience.

To determine the latent factors of smoking cessation, a factor analysis was carried out when interrelated variables were combined into more general categories — groups of factors.

The first factor, called by us "real (current) negative physiological effects", included the following variables: problems with bad breath, tooth color, skin type, cough, loss of physical fitness. These are the results of the influence of tobacco smoking on the body, which manifest themselves even with a short duration of consumption.

During the experiment, the accuracy of reproduction of a given sample was measured by first alternating, and then simultaneously pressing the right and left hands of the subjects on the keys of the measuring device. The measurements were carried out on a device specially made for the examination, which allows you to set the value of the reproduction error automatically directly during operation. A series of measurements were carried out in different psychoemotional states of the subjects: calm wakefulness and in a state of psychoemotional excitement (after intense physical exertion). The comparative correlation of the obtained results confirmed the hypothesis put forward by the author about the influence of the psychoemotional state of the subject and local interhemispheric interactions on the accuracy of perception and subsequent reproduction of a given sample, and also clarified the "contribution" of interhemispheric asymmetry to the accuracy of reproduction of the perceptual sample. In the course of the study, it was found that the most informative measurement to establish the perceptual maturity of the subject is the magnitude of the error in perception and subsequent reproduction of the sample by the leading hand in a state of calm wakefulness.

Results and their discussion. At the time of the survey, only 7.5% of doctors noted the fact of adherence to smoking, another 2.5% had smoked in the past. It is possible that such a low percentage of smokers is a regional feature, since much higher figures are found in domestic sources devoted to this problem. Some authors

have studied smoking among all categories of health workers, including both doctors and average medical staff. At the same time, smoking of nursing staff was more frequent compared to doctors. Smoking men were 4.2 times more. It is encouraging that with an increase in medical experience of more than 5 years, the total number of smokers was halved. Not all smoking doctors noted this as a problem for their health (5% vs. 7.5%). For comparison: among the actual problems for their own health, most doctors named excess body weight (36%). For women, this problem was 3 times more urgent. At the same time, 17.5% of respondents noted the irrationality of their diet. Thus, smoking seemed to doctors to be a much smaller problem compared to some others.

None of the interviewed doctors named "overweight reduction" as the reason for smoking, a fairly common opinion among the non-medical part of the population. At the same time, smoking cigarettes to a certain extent really reduces appetite and this is directly proportional to the number of cigarettes smoked. Thus, a decrease in appetite is achieved by increasing the nicotine load, and therefore increasing the harmful effects of tobacco smoke components. At the same time, for patients with chronic obstructive pulmonary disease - a disease from which mortality is increasing at a progressive rate among both men and women and for which smoking is the most important risk factor, lack of body weight is a risk factor for an unfavorable outcome of the disease.

Despite the low smoking rate among the interviewed doctors, attention should be paid to potentially very negative factors: a more significant smoking rate among young doctors, a high conjugacy of tobacco and hookah smoking, a frivolous attitude to electronic cigarettes and the threat of tobacco addiction. These factors can significantly weaken the effectiveness of the fight against smoking in the general population. In this regard, it is necessary to continue active anti-tobacco propaganda, including at the state level with legislative support, paying significant attention to the medical environment.

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